

A STUDY ON CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT IN STATE BANK OF INDIA (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE)

***A.Y.Ketti Ramalingam**

Assistant Professor, School Of Commerce-PG,
Rathnavel Subramaniam College Of Arts & Science (Autonomous),
Sulur, Coimbatore.

****Lima Alphonse**

II M.Com Student School Of Commerce-PG,
Rathnavel Subramaniam College Of Arts & Science (Autonomous),
Sulur, Coimbatore.

*****Lisha Alphonse**

II M.Com Student School Of Commerce-PG,
Rathnavel Subramaniam College Of Arts & Science (Autonomous),
Sulur, Coimbatore.

Abstract

Today banks are dealing with several challenges including global competition for Deposits, Loans, and underwriting fees, increasing customer demands, shrinking profit margins: and need to keep up with the new technologies. Banks have realized the importance of Customer relationship management (CRM) and its potential to help them to acquire new customers, retain existing ones, and maximize their lifetime value. Bank s has realized that CRM is the only solution to help them to maintain a long term relationship with their customers. On the other hand, maintaining relationships with customers also requires strong coordination between different departments at the bank viz., IT, Sales, Service, Support, and Marketing. CRM came from the origins and is based on the principles of Relationship marketing which is considered as one of the key departmental areas of modern marketing and the one which generated great research interest over several years.

INTRODUCTION

CRM came in to existence when banking institutions have started to become more and more competitive. The focus of CRM increased banks abilities to understand the customers' current needs more precisely and also helped them to understand their customers behaviors, such as what they have done in the past , and what they plan to do in the future. Such practice helped banks to design strategies based on each customer's preference in order to meet their customer's needs. Customer information is important for banks and the intelligent use of such information would create long term, two way relationships with customers.

Customer Relationship Management is the establishment, development, maintenance and optimization of long-term mutually valuable relationships between consumers and the organizations. Successful customer relationship management focuses on understanding the needs and desires of the customers and is achieved by placing these needs at the heart of the business by integrating them with the organization's strategy, people, technology and business processes.

At the heart of a perfect CRM strategy is the creation of mutual value for all the parties involved in the business process. It is about creating a sustainable competitive advantage by being the best at understanding, communicating, and delivering, and developing existing customer relationships in addition to creating and keeping new customers. CRM in banking is a key element of differentiation that allows a bank to develop its customer base and sales capacity. The goal of CRM is to manage all aspects of customer interactions in a manner that enables banks to maximize profitability from every customer. Increasing competition, deregulation, and the internet have all contributed to the increase in customer power. Technology has reduced barriers to entry and exit for the customers, making it easier to switch banks or brokers without feeling the pinch in the wallet. Retaining customers is a major concern for banking institutions which underscores the importance of customer relationship management (CRM).

PRINCIPLES OF CRM

“Customer relationship is our most valuable asset; don’t trust them to judge anyone.”

- ❖ Customer focus
- ❖ Leadership
- ❖ Process approach
- ❖ System approach
- ❖ Involvement of people
- ❖ Mutually beneficial customer relationship

BENEFITS OF CRM

- ❖ CRM Banking Focuses on the Customer
- ❖ Satisfied Customers
- ❖ Centralized Information
- ❖ CRM Banking Boosts Small Banks
- ❖ Customer Segregation
- ❖ Aggressive Customer Acquisition
- ❖ Improved Cross-sell Framework
- ❖ Increased Operational Efficiencies and Collaboration
- ❖ Lower Total Cost of Ownership
- ❖ Campaign Management
- ❖ Customer Information Consolidation
- ❖ 360-degree view of company
- ❖ Personalized sales home page
- ❖ Operational Inefficiency Removal
- ❖ CRM with Business Intelligence

CHALLENGES AND IMPLEMENTATION OF CRM

- ❖ The difficulty of obtaining a complete view of customers.
- ❖ The need to move away from disjointed, standalone, and inconsistent channels to provide a cohesive, multichannel offering.
- ❖ The burden of disconnected legacy systems and disparate databases that store client financial data.
- ❖ The cost and complexity of meeting stringent government regulatory and client security and privacy requirements.
- ❖ The pressure on margins and growth prospects from increased competition.
- ❖ The costs associated with retaining customers and developing customer loyalty.

According to CRM software firm People soft, banks need to be aware of key problems:

- ❖ Measuring CRM benefits
- ❖ Customer profitability

METHOD OF EFFECTIVE CRM IMPLEMENTATION

- ❖ Acknowledge email enquiries
- ❖ Develop the right contact strategy
- ❖ Providing online `chatting
- ❖ Reduce costs by improving website design and self-service
- ❖ Analyses the project's scope
- ❖ Know thy limitations
- ❖ Change accounts into customer

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- ✓ To diagnose the customer relationship management in banking sector for relationship between the customer and banks.
- ✓ To study and discuss the existing CRM models in the State banks of India.
- ✓ To analyze the CRM strategies adopted and the perception of employees.
- ✓ To uncover the similarities and differences in the overall CRM operation.
- ✓ To ascertain the challenges and issues with CRM adoption within the banking industry.
- ✓ To offer suggestions to improve banks efficiency through effective CRM.

NEED FOR THE STUDY

The banking industry was selected for CRM research because, in general banks are more advanced in terms of technology adoption than many other organizations. The reasons is that other organizations do not usually require the level of information from their customers which banks do; banks keeps a lot of in depth information about their customers. Therefore, the CRM system currently used in banks need to be more robust to be able to handle such sensitive information about different types of customers.

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY

Methodology presents the Sampling design, Data sources, Tools for data collection, Construction of questionnaire, Pilot study the Frame work of analysis.

SAMPLING DESIGN- The primary data was collected through the field survey in the study area. The second questionnaire was collected from 60 customers utilizing the services of SBI. The study used both primary data and secondary data. The focus of the study is to analyze the attitude, perception of employees and customers towards the CRM strategies adopted in the SBI in Coimbatore.

CONSTRUCTION OF QUESTIONNAIRE - Questionnaire was a main tool used to collect the pertinent data from the selected 60 customers. The research problem and questionnaire were framed accordingly with the help of the guide comments and Research Experts.

PILOT STUDY- The questionnaire was pre-tested with a few samples among the selected sample respondents in the study areas. Taking into consideration the suggestion of the selected sample respondents, necessary modifications and changes were incorporated in the questionnaire after the pilot study.

FRAME WORK OF ANALYSIS- The following tools of analysis were used in the study. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the data and draw the inference.

PERCENTAGE ANALYSIS- The frequency distribution (Descriptive/percentage analysis) of the variables were calculated with help of simple percentage, by writing the formula $FD = f_1/n * 100$. Where f_1 denotes the number of respondents, and n denotes the total number of sample population.

TWO-WAY ANALYSIS -A statistical analysis in which two independent variables, or factors, are examined with regard to their impact on a dependent variable and on one another. For example, a researcher might want to examine the effect of age and sex on productivity. The researcher would examine the effect of age on productivity, the effect of sex on productivity, and the effect of different combinations of age and sex on productivity.

WEIGHTED AVERAGE RANK ANALYSIS- The attitude of the consumers may vary from one aspect to another. In order to analyse the attitude of the consumers using various services, the average analysis is performed to identify the attitude of the consumers and dealers separately. Based on the consolidated opinion of the respondents, the average rank is calculated and final rank is allotted using the criterion “more the average rank more is the priority”.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study suffers from the following limitations

- ❖ The study is limited to Coimbatore area and therefore the findings of the study cannot be extended to other areas.
- ❖ The restricted sample size was one of the major limitations.
- ❖ Detailed study was not possible due to limit.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Peppers and Rogers (1999)¹ argued that other organizations view CRM as a tool, which has been particularly designed for one-to-one customer communications, which is the function of sales, call centres or the marketing departments.

Galbreth and Rogers (1999)² that CRM helps a business organization to fully understand which customers are worthwhile to acquire, which to keep, which have untapped potential, which are strategic, which are important, profitable and which should be abandoned.

Kotler (2000)³ assured that CRM uses IT to gather data, which can then be used to develop information acquired to create a more personal interaction with the customer. In the long-term, it produces a method of continuous analysis and reinforcement in order to enhance customer's lifetime value with firms.

Peppard (2000)⁴ noted that effective management of information⁴ has a very important role to play in CRM because it can be used to for product tailoring, service innovation; consolidate views of customers, and for calculating customer lifetime value.

*Goldenberg (2000)*⁵ believes that CRM is not merely technology applications for marketing, sales and services but rather when it is successfully implemented ; it enables firms to have cross-functional , customer-driven , technology-integrated business process management strategy that maximises relationships.

STATE BANK OF INDIA

State Bank of India (SBI) is a banking and financial services company based in India. It is a state-owned corporation with its headquarters in Mumbai, Maharashtra. As of March 2012, it had assets of US\$360 billion and 14,119 branches, including 157 foreign offices in 32 countries across the globe making it the largest banking and financial services company in India. The bank traces its ancestry to British India, through the Imperial Bank of India, to the founding in 1806 of the Bank of Calcutta, making it the oldest commercial bank in the Indian Subcontinent. Bank of Madras merged into the other two presidency banks—Bank of Calcutta and Bank of Bombay—to form the Imperial Bank of India, which in turn became the State Bank of India. The Government of India nationalised the Imperial Bank of India in 1955, with the Reserve Bank of India taking a 60% stake, and renamed it the State Bank of India. In 2008, the government took over the stake held by the Reserve Bank of India. SBI has been ranked 285th in the Fortune Global 500 rankings of the world's biggest corporations for the year 2012. SBI provides a range of banking products through its network of branches in India and overseas, including products aimed at non-resident Indians(NRIs). SBI has 14 regional hubs and 57 Zonal Offices that are located at important cities throughout the country.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

TABLE 1 SHOWING AGE OF THE RESPONDENT

AGE	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
LESS THAN 25 YEARS	12	20
26 YEARS – 35 YEARS	24	40
36 YEARS – 45 YEARS	12	20
46 YEARS ABOVE	12	20
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - The above table shows the age of the respondents. Out of the total respondents taken for study, highest 40 percent of the respondents belong to 26-35 years of age, 20 percent of the respondents belong to age of group 36-45 years, 20 percent of the respondents below 25 years and the remaining 20 percent of the respondents belong to above 46 years. Majority of the respondents are 26-35 years of age.

TABLE 2 SHOWING GENDER OF THE RESPONDENT

GENDER	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
MALE	44	73.33
FEMALE	16	26.67
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - The table shows the gender of the respondents. Out of the total respondents taken for the study, 73.33% of the respondents are male and another 26.67% are female. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that most of the respondents are male.

TABLE 3 SHOWING MARITAL STATUS OF THE RESPONDENT

MARITAL STATUS	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
MARRIED	38	63.33
UNMARRIED	22	36.67
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION -The above table depicts the marital status of the respondents. Out of the total respondents taken for the study, 63.33% of the respondents are married and another 36.67% are unmarried. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that most of the respondents are married.

TABLE 4 SHOWING EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND OF THE RESPONDENT

QUALIFICATION	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGH SCHOOL	12	20
BACHELOR DEGREE	18	30

MASTER DEGREE	16	26.7
OTHERS	14	23.3
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION -It is understood from the table that out of the total respondents taken for study 30 percent of the respondents have completed the bachelor degree, 26.67 percent are master degree, another 20 percent have their high school, and 23.3 percent of the respondents are others. Majority of the respondents have completed their bachelor degree.

TABLE 5 SHOWING OCCUPATION OF THE RESPONDENT

OCCUPATION	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
PROFESSIONAL	20	33.3
BUSINESSMEN	12	20
INDUSTRIALIST	8	13.3
SERVICE SECTOR	6	10
AGRICULTURIST	6	10
OTHERS	8	13.3
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION -The table clearly shows the occupation of the respondents. Out of the total respondents taken for the study 33.33% of the respondents are professional, 20% of the respondents belong to businessmen, 10% of the respondents are agriculturists, 10% of the respondents belong to service sector and the remaining 13.3% of the respondent belongs to others. Majority of the respondents are professional.

TABLE 6 SHOWING THE EARNING HANDS OF THE RESPONDENT

EARNING HANDS	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
ONE	12	20
TWO	16	26.7
THREE	18	30
MORE THAN THREE	14	23.3
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION -The above table shows the earning hands of the respondents. Out of the total respondents taken for the study 30 percent of the respondents have 3 members earning in the family, 26.7 percent of the respondents have 2 members earning, 23.3 percent of the respondents have more than 3 members earning, and the remaining 20 percent of the respondents have 1 members earning in the family. Majority of the respondents have 3 members earning in the family.

TABLE 7 SHOWING THE ANNUAL INCOME OF THE RESPONDENT

ANNUAL INCOME	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
LESS THAN 1 lakhs	14	23.3
BETWEEN 1 lakhs – 2 lakhs	16	26.7
BETWEEN 2 lakhs – 3 lakhs	18	30
ABOVE 3 lakhs	12	20
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - The table clearly shows the annual income of the respondents. 30% of respondents are getting the annual income of Rs. 2,00,000-3,00,000 , 26.7% of the respondents are getting the income of Rs. 1,00,000-2,00,000, 23.3% of the respondents are getting income less than Rs.1,00,000 , remaining 20% of the respondents are getting income above Rs.3,00,000. Majority of the respondents are earning between Rs. 2, 00,000 - 3, 00,000

TABLE 8 SHOWING THE ACCOUNT TYPE OF THE RESPONDENT

ACCOUNT TYPE	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
SAVINGS ACCOUNT	28	46.7
CURRENT ACCOUNT	8	13.3
OVERDRAFT ACCOUNT	6	10
CASH CREDIT ACCOUNT	2	3.3
LOAN ACCOUNT	10	16.7
OTHERS	6	10
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - The above table shows the account type of the respondents. Out of the total respondents taken for the study 46.7% of the respondents have savings account, 16.7% of the respondents have loan account, 13.3% of the respondents have current account, 10% of the respondents have overdraft account, 3.3% of the respondents have cash credit account and remaining 10% of the respondents have others. Majority of the respondents have savings account.

TABLE 9 SHOWING ACCOUNT STATEMENTS THROUGH THE MAIL OR INTERNET

ACCOUNT STATEMENTS	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	41	68.3
AGREE	7	11.7

NEUTRAL	6	10
DISAGREE	4	6.7
HIGHLY DISAGREE	2	3.3
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - It is understood from the table that out of the total respondents taken for study, 68.3% of the respondents highly agree with the statement, 11.7% of the respondents agree with the statement, 10% of the respondent says neutral, 6.7% of the respondents disagree the statements and remaining 3.3% of the respondents highly disagree the statement. Majority of the respondents highly agree with the statement.

TABLE 10 SHOWING BANKING PRODUCTS AND SERVICES

RELATIONSHIP	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	4	6.7
AGREE	26	43.3
NEUTRAL	12	20
DISAGREE	10	16.7
HIGHLY DISAGREE	8	13.3
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - From the data given above, it is clear that 43.3 percent of the respondents says as agree, another 20 percent of the respondents views as neutral, 16.7 percent view as disagree and 13.3 percent of the respondents says as highly disagree, remaining 6.7 of the respondents views as highly agree. Thus from the table it is found that 43.3 percent of the respondents agree with the statement.

TABLE 11 SHOWING VALUE FOR MONEY

VALUE FOR MONEY	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	32	53.3
AGREE	12	20
NEUTRAL	6	10
DISAGREE	6	10
HIGHLY DISAGREE	4	6.7
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - As the value given above, 53.3 percent of the respondents says as highly agree, another 20 percent of the respondents views as agree, and 10 percent of the respondents says as disagree, 10 percent of the respondents says as neutral, remaining 6.7 percent of the respondents views as highly disagree. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 53.3 percent of the respondents highly agree with the statement.

TABLE 12 SHOWING REPUTATION FOR USING HIGHLY SKILLED EMPLOYEES

SKILLED EMPLOYEES	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	6	10
AGREE	14	23.3
NEUTRAL	22	36.7
DISAGREE	8	13.3
HIGHLY DISAGREE	10	16.7

TOTAL	60	100
--------------	-----------	------------

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - The above table indicates 36.7 percent of the respondents says as neutral, another 23.3 percent of the respondents views as agree, and 16.7 percent of the respondents says as highly disagree, 13.3 percent of the respondents says as disagree, remaining 10 percent of the respondents views as highly agree. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 36.7 percent of the respondents are neutral with the statement.

TABLE 13 SHOWING BANK TREATS INFORMATION EXCHANGED CONFIDENTIALLY

CONFIDENTIAL	NO.OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	38	63.3
AGREE	2	3.3
NEUTRAL	10	16.7
DISAGREE	6	10
HIGHLY DISAGREE	4	6.7
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION -As the value given above, 63.3 percent of the respondents says as highly agree, another 16.7 percent of the respondents views as neutral, and 10 percent of the respondents says as disagree, 6.7 percent of the respondents says as highly disagree remaining 3.3 percent of the respondents views as agree. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 63.3 percent of the respondents highly agree with the statement.

TABLE 14 SHOWING IMPORTANT BANKING INFORMATION THROUGH VARIOUS MEDIA

INFORMS	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	14	23.3
AGREE	24	40

NEUTRAL	8	13.3
DISAGREE	8	13.3
HIGHLY DISAGREE	6	10
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - The above table shows the views of the respondents taken for study, 40% of the respondents agree the statement, 23.3% of the respondents highly agree the statement, 13.3% of the respondents view as neutral, 13.3% of the respondents disagree the statement and 10% of the respondents highly disagree with the statement. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 40% of the respondents agree the statement.

TABLE 15 SHOWING MEASUREMENTS TO ENSURE THE SECURITY OF MY FUNDS

SECURITY	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	40	66.7
AGREE	12	20
NEUTRAL	4	6.7
DISAGREE	2	3.3
HIGHLY DISAGREE	2	3.3
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - The above table indicates 66.7 percent of the respondents says as highly agree, another 20 percent of the respondents views as agree, and 6.7 percent of the respondents says as neutral, 3.3 percent of the respondents says as disagree, remaining 3.3 percent of the respondents views as highly disagree. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 66.7 percent of the respondents view as highly agree.

TABLE 16 SHOWING HIGH ETHICAL STANDARDS IN ITS SERVICE DELIVERY

SERVICE DELIVERY	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	10	16.7
AGREE	12	20
NEUTRAL	14	23.3

DISAGREE	10	16.7
HIGHLY DISAGREE	14	23.3
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION- From the table it is found that 23.3 percent of the respondents says as neutral, another 23.3 percent of the respondents views as highly disagree, and 16.7 percent of the respondents says as disagree, 16.7 percent of the respondents says as highly agree, remaining 20 percent of the respondents views as agree. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 23.3 percent of the respondents view as highly disagree and also neutral.

TABLE 17 SHOWING VARIETIES OF SERVICES

SERVICES	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	8	13.3
AGREE	12	20
NEUTRAL	16	26.7
DISAGREE	12	20
HIGHLY DISAGREE	12	20
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - The above table shows the views of the respondents taken for study, 26.7% of the respondents are neutral, 20% of the respondents highly disagree the statement, 20% of the respondent views as disagree, 20% of the respondents agree the statement and 13.3% of the respondents highly agree with the statement. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 26.7% of the respondents are neutral.

TABLE 18 SHOWING TECHNOLOGICALLY ADVANCED SERVICE, INTERNET BANKING

TECHNOLOGY	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	22	36.7
AGREE	16	26.7

NEUTRAL	10	16.7
DISAGREE	6	10
HIGHLY DISAGREE	6	10
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - The table above depicts the views of the respondents taken for study, 36.7% of the respondents highly agree, 26.7% of the respondents agree the statement, 16.7% of the respondent views as neutral, 10% of the respondents disagree the statement and 10% of the respondents highly disagree with the statement. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 36.7% of the respondents are highly agree.

TABLE 19 SHOWING THE EMPLOYEES OF MY BANK KNOW HOW TO COPE WITH ALL TYPES OF CLIENTS

TYPES OF CLIENTS	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	8	13.3
AGREE	20	33.3
NEUTRAL	10	16.7
DISAGREE	12	20
HIGHLY DISAGREE	10	16.7
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION -From the above table, 33.3 percent of the respondents says as agree, another 16.7 percent of the respondents views as highly disagree, and 16.7 percent of the respondents says as neutral, 13.3 percent of the respondents says as highly agree, remaining 20 percent of the respondents views as disagree. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 33.3 percent of the respondents view as agree.

TABLE 20 SHOWING MY BANK'S SERVICE QUALITY DEPENDS ON ITS CLIENTS' NEEDS

SERVICE QUALITY	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	10	16.7
AGREE	22	36.7
NEUTRAL	10	16.7

DISAGREE	10	16.7
HIGHLY DISAGREE	8	13.3
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - It is understood from the table, 36.7% of the respondents are agree, 16.7% of the respondents disagree the statement, 16.7% of the respondent views as highly agree, 16.7% of the respondents disagree the statement and 13.3% of the respondents highly disagree with the statement. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 36.7% of the respondents agree.

TABLE 21 SHOWING BANK BASED ON ITS FEES FOR SERVICES

FEES FOR SERVICES	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	8	13.3
AGREE	10	16.7
NEUTRAL	14	23.3
DISAGREE	16	26.7
HIGHLY DISAGREE	12	20
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - From the table above, 26.7% of the respondents disagree, 23.3% of the respondents are neutral, 20% of the respondent views as highly disagree, 16.7% of the respondents agree with the statement and 13.3% of the respondents highly agree with the statement. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 26.7% of the respondents disagree.

TABLE 22 SHOWING THE OVERALL RELATIONSHIP WITH MY BANK

SATISFIED	NO. OF RESPONDENT	PERCENTAGE
HIGHLY AGREE	6	10
	30	50

AGREE		
NEUTRAL	8	13.3
DISAGREE	6	10
HIGHLY DISAGREE	10	16.7
TOTAL	60	100

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INTERPRETATION - The above table indicates 50 percent of the respondents says as agree, another 16.7 percent of the respondents views as highly disagree, and 13.3 percent of the respondents says as neutral, 10 percent of the respondents says as disagree, remaining 10 percent of the respondents views as highly agree. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 50 percent of the respondents agree with the statement

TWO WAY ANALYSIS

“RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE ATTRIBUTE OF THE EMPLOYEES OF MY BANK TOWARDS CLIENTS INFLUENCES MY RELATIONSHIP WITH MY BANK AND THE AGE GROUP OF THE RESPONDENTS”

AGE GROUP ATTRIBUTE OF THE EMPLOYEES	LESS THAN 25 YEARS	26-35 YEARS	36-45 YEARS	46 YEARS ABOVE	TOTAL
HIGHLY DISAGREE	0	1	2(24)	2(24)	5
DISAGREE	0	2(20)	3(30)	1(10)	6

NEUTRAL	1(5)	6(30)	3(15)	2(10)	12
AGREE	8(17.14)	11(23.57)	3(6.42)	6(12.85)	28
HIGHLY AGREE	3(20)	4(26.66)	1(6.66)	1(6.66)	9
TOTAL	12	24	12	12	60

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INFERENCE- The above table shows that 20% of the respondents in the age group of less than 25years have stated that the attribute of the employees of my bank towards clients influences my relationship with my bank of employees is highly agree, 30% of the respondents in the age group of 36-35 years stated that it is neutral. 30% of the respondents in the age group of 36-45 years have stated that they disagree. Majority of the respondents in the age group of 36-35 years stated that it is neutral.

“RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN THE SECURITY OF MY FUNDS AND GENDER”.

GENDER	MALE	FEMALE	TOTAL
THE SECURITY OF MY FUNDS			
HIGHLY DISAGREE	1 (30)	1(30)	2
DISAGREE	1(30)	1(30)	2

NEUTRAL	4(20)	0	4
AGREE	4(20)	8(40)	12
HIGHLY AGREE	20(30)	20(30)	40
TOTAL	30	30	60

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

INFERENCE- The above table shows that 30% of the male respondents have highly agree that their relationship with bank depends on whether it implements strict measurements to ensure the security of their funds, where as 40% of the female respondents agree with the statement.

WEIGHTED AVERAGE RANK WITH VARIOUS MODE

Particulars	HA	A	N	DA	HDA	Total	WA	Rank
Account Statements	205	28	18	4	2	261	5220	1
Value For Money	160	48	18	12	4	242	4840	3
Promised Times	60	88	36	16	6	206	4120	4
Skilled Employees	30	56	66	16	10	178	3560	5
Confidential	190	8	30	12	4	244	4880	2

It is inferred that account statements are given first preference by the respondents. Second rank was given to confidential of the data and third rank goes to the value for money and so on.

WEIGHTED AVERAGE RANK WITH VARIOUS SERVICES & CHARGES

Particulars	HA	A	N	DA	HDA	Total	WA	Rank
Service Delivery	50	48	42	20	14	174	3480	3
Different Fees Charged	30	40	66	28	8	172	3440	4
Advanced services	110	64	30	12	6	222	4440	1
Fees For Services	40	40	42	32	12	166	3320	5
Satisfied With Overall Service	30	88	24	32	8	182	3640	2

(Source: Computed from Primary Data)

From the above table it is suggested that respondents gives first rank to advanced services. Second rank to satisfactory level of overall services and third rank to service delivery.

FINDINGS SUGGESSTIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

THE MAJOR FINDINGS ARE,

1. Majority of the respondents are 26-35 years of age.
2. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that most of the respondents are male.
3. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that most of the respondents are married.
4. Majority of the respondents have completed their bachelor degree.
5. Majority of the respondents are professional.
6. Majority of the respondents have 3 members earning in the family.
7. Majority of the respondents are earning between Rs. 2, 00,000 - 3, 00,000
8. Majority of the respondents have savings account.
9. Majority of the respondents highly agree with the statement.
10. Thus from the table it is found that 43.3 percent of the respondents agree with the statement.
11. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 53.3 percent of the respondents highly agree with the statement.
12. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 36.7 percent of the respondents are neutral with the statement
13. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 63.3 percent of the respondents highly agree with the statement.
14. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 40% of the respondents agree the statement.
15. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 66.7 percent of the respondents view as highly agree.

16. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 23.3 percent of the respondents view as highly disagree and also neutral.
17. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 26.7% of the respondents are neutral.
18. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 36.7% of the respondents are highly agree.
19. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 33.3 percent of the respondents view as agree.
20. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 36.7% of the respondents agree.
21. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 26.7% of the respondents disagree.
22. Thus from the analysis it could be concluded that 50 percent of the respondents agree with the statement

SUGGESTION

Customer support is directly connected to CRM. If a company fails to provide quality customer support, they have also failed with their CRM system. When a customer makes complaints, they must be handled quickly and efficiently. The company should also seek to make sure those mistakes are not repeated. When sales are made, they should be tracked so that the company can analyze them from various aspects. It is also important to understand the architecture of Customer relationship management.

The architecture of CRM can be broken down into three categories, and these are collaborative, operational, and analytical. The collaborative aspect of CRM deals with communication between companies and their clients. The operational aspect of the architecture deals with the concept of making certain processes automated. The analytical aspect of CRM architecture deals with analyzing customer information and using it for business intelligence purposes. Each one of these elements is critical for the success of a CRM system. A company must learn how to use all three properly, and when they do this proficiently, they will be able to build strong customer relationships and ensure their profits for a long period of time. As more businesses continue to compete on a global level, it will become more important for them to use successful Customer relationship management techniques.

CONCLUSION

There are a number of reasons why CRM has become so important in the last 10 years. The competition in the global market has become highly competitive, and it has become easier for customers to switch companies if they are not happy with the service they receive. One of the primary goals of CRM is to maintain clients. When it is used effectively, a company will be able to build a relationship with their customers that can last a lifetime. Customer relationship management tools will generally come in the form of software. Each software program may vary in the way it approaches CRM. It is important to realize that CRM is more than just a technology.

Customer relationship management could be better defined as being a methodology, an approach that a company will use to achieve their goals. It should be directly connected to the philosophy of the company. It must guide all of its policies, and it must be an important part of customer service and marketing. If this is not done, the CRM system will become a failure. There are a number of things the ideal CRM system should have. It should allow the company to find the factors that interest their customers the most. A company must realize that it is impossible for them to succeed if they do not cater to the desires and needs of their customers. Customer relationship management is a powerful system that will allow them to do this. It is also important for the company to use measures that are dependent on their customers. This will greatly tip the odds of success in their favor. While CRM should not be viewed as a technology, it is important to realize that there are end to end processes that must be created so that customers can be properly served. In many cases, these processes will use computers and software.